

Extreme Temperature in Burkina Faso: Decadal Spatio-Temporal Changes Between 1960 and 2019

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Abstract:

Studies carried out in Burkina Faso focus on rainfall, leaving aside those relating to maximum temperatures, which can have repercussions on human health and the environment. The main objective of this study is to analyse the dynamics of maximum temperatures between 1960 and 2019, using Worldclim satellite data on maximum temperatures. Data processing was based on zonal statistics and spatial analyses, using QGIS software. The study shows that maximum temperatures increased between 1969 and 2019. Average maximum temperatures were high during the period 1960-1969, at 35°C. Thereafter, average maximum temperatures fell to

33°C between 1970 and 1979 and 32°C between 1980 and 1999. However, they rose again between 200-2019, with maximum temperatures of 34°C. These maximum temperatures vary very little (CV less than 20%) over the period 1969-2019. Seasonal variability in maximum temperatures has also been observed, with a significant increase in maximum temperatures during the dry season compared with the rainy season. It is therefore important for the government of Burkina Faso to take urgent measures to protect vulnerable groups (the elderly and children) from heat waves resulting from rising maximum temperatures.

Keywords: *Dynamic, Temperature maximum, Burkina Faso, Seasonal variation in maximum temperatures.*

Introduction

Climate variability is affecting many countries around the world (IPCC, 2022). In West Africa, it manifests itself in rising temperatures, disrupted precipitation patterns and increased extreme weather events (IPCC, 2021). but most studies focus on rainfall parameters at regional (Le Barbé et al., 2002; Nicholson, 2013; Nouaceur & Murarescu, 2020) and local (Ahokpossi, 2018; Yanogo & Yameogo, 2023) scales. As a result, scientists have a better understanding of rainfall behaviour. However,

certain climatic parameters, such as temperature, are little used. Temperatures (maximum, minimum) have increased significantly between 1960 and 2010 (Barry et al., 2018). This rise in temperature could lead to an increase in diseases such as malaria in West African countries (Diouf et al., 2020). Researchers are therefore looking at the statistical analysis of temperature trends (minimum, maximum) (Bambara et al., 2018). In addition, the spatio-temporal dynamics of temperatures have been addressed by several authors (Quenum et al., 2020; Nour-Eldeen et al., 2020). However, very few focus on the spatial

and temporal analysis of temperatures at the local scale. Therefore, it seems important to strengthen the literature on spatio-temporal evolution at the local scale. The main objective of this study is therefore to analyze the spatial and temporal evolution of temperatures in Burkina Faso.

Data and Methods

Study Area and Data Sources

The study area is located in West Africa. It is subdivided into four phytogeographic zones: the strict Sahel, the sub-Saharan, the northern Sudanian and the southern Sudanian (figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of the study area

Temperature (maximal) data were obtained from the worldclim data site (<https://www.worldclim.org/data/worldclim21.html>). The acquired data have a spatial resolution of 30 seconds. This is data raster. Each downloaded year contains 12 months of satellite images in GeoTiff (.tiff) format. The study period includes decadal data (1960-1969; 1970-1979; 1980-1989; 1990-1999; 2000-2009; 2010-2019).

Method of Data Analysis

It is based on spatial analysis, zonal statistics and coefficient of variation (CV). Spatial analysis was used to map temperature extremes in Burkina Faso between 1960 and 2019. It involved merging satellite images and then cutting them with Shapefile of Burkina Faso.

Zonal statistics such as mean, standard deviation and min and max were obtained using QGIS software, with the following process: Processing Toolbox → Raster Analysis → Zonal Statistics. In addition, the coefficient of variation (CV) was used. This corresponds to the annual standard deviation divided by the mean (Medvigy & Beaulieu, 2012).

Its formula is as follow:

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of extreme temperatures and μ is the annual average of extreme temperatures.

CV was used to assess the degree of variability of extreme temperatures in Burkina Faso over the period 1960 to 2019. The CV is used to classify the level of temperature variability as follows: low ($CV < 20$), moderate ($20 < CV < 30$), high ($CV > 30$), very high, $CV > 40\%$ and $CV > 70\%$ indicate extremely high interannual temperature variability (Hayelom et al., 2017).

Results

Characteristics of Zonal Statistics and Coefficients of Variation for Maximum Temperatures

The zonal statistics cover the period from 1960 to 2019, but are divided into decades. Thus, for the decade 1960-1969. The average maximum temperature evolves according to the regions of Burkina Faso (Table 1).

Table 1. Maximum Temperature Over the Period 1960-1969 in Burkina Faso

N°	Name of region	Mean	Stdev	Min	Max	CV
1	Boucle du Mouhoun	35.22	0.88	32	37	2.5
2	Cascades	34.43	0.61	33	36	1.77
3	Central	35.23	0.42	35	36	1.19

4	Centre-East	37.05	0.46	35	38	1.24
5	Center	35.94	0.45	35	37	1.25
6	Central-West	35.93	0.32	35	37	0.89
7	South Central	36.25	0.57	35	37	1.57
8	East	36.90	0.71	36	39	1.92
9	Hauts-Bassins	34.49	0.84	33	37	2.44
10	North	34.89	0.55	34	36	1.58
11	Plateau-Central	35.84	0.66	35	37	1.84
12	Sahel	36.02	0.49	35	37	1.36
13	SouthWest	35.59	0.62	34	37	1.74

Source: Worldclim,1960-1969

For the periods 1970-1979, 1980-1989, 1990-1999, 2000-2009, 2010-2019. Average maximum

temperatures vary from region to region. CVs are low in all countries.

Table 2. Maximum Temperature Over the Period 1970-1999 in Burkina Faso

1970-1979						
N°	Name of region	Mean	stdev	Min	Max	CV
1	Boucle du Mouhoun	32.70	0.936	30	34	2.86
2	Cascades	32.10	0.497	31	33	1.55
3	Central	32.14	0.342	32	33	1.06
4	Centre-East	33.62	0.564	32	35	1.68
5	North Central	32.14	0.355	31	33	1.1
6	Central-West	33.21	0.528	32	34	1.59
7	South Central	33.25	0.598	32	34	1.8
8	East	33.27	0.834	32	35	2.51
9	Hauts-Bassins	32.35	0.776	31	34	2.4
10	North	31.82	0.541	31	33	1.7
11	Plateau-Central	32.52	0.500	32	33	1.54
12	Sahel	31.95	0.272	31	33	0.85
13	SouthWest	33.36	0.657	32	34	1.97
1980-1989						
N°	Name of region	mean	stdev	Min	Max	CV
1	Boucle du Mouhoun	33.40	0.87	31	35	2.6
2	Cascades	32.79	0.44	31	34	1.34
3	Central	32.89	0.39	32	34	1.19
4	Centre-East	34.39	0.74	33	36	2.15
5	North Central	33.00	0.08	32	34	0.24
6	Central-West	33.83	0.58	33	35	1.71
7	South Central	33.84	0.66	32	35	1.95
8	East	33.94	0.95	33	36	2.8
9	Hauts-Bassins	32.79	0.79	31	35	2.41
10	North	32.89	0.36	32	34	1.09
11	Plateau-Central	33.26	0.45	32	34	1.35
12	Sahel	33.01	0.10	33	34	0.3
13	SouthWest	33.85	0.62	33	35	1.83
1990-1999						
n°	Name of region	Mean	Stdev	Min	Max	CV
1	Boucle du Mouhoun	33.00	0.91	30	34	2.76
2	Cascades	32.60	0.57	31	33	1.75
3	Central	33.00	0.41	32	34	1.24

4	Centre-East	34.79	0.64	33	36	1.84
5	North Central	33.24	0.43	32	34	1.29
6	Central-West	33.66	0.48	33	35	1.43
7	South Central	33.98	0.68	33	35	2
8	East	34.59	0.83	33	37	2.4
9	Hauts-Bassins	32.43	0.78	31	34	2.41
10	North	32.63	0.48	32	33	1.47
11	Plateau-Central	33.42	0.51	32	34	1.53
12	Sahel	33.20	0.41	32	34	1.23
13	SouthWest	33.62	0.55	32	35	1.64

Source: Worldclim,1970-1999

This table shows that average maximum temperatures fell between 1970 and 1999 compared with the 1960-1969 decade. However, during the periods 1970-1979 and 1980-1989, average maximum temperatures were lower than in the decade 1990-1999. 1980-1989. Average maximum temperatures were lower than in 1990-1999. In fact, over the period 1970-1999,

the average temperature was between 31°C and 33°C. Over the period 1980-1989, it fluctuated between 33°C and 34°C.

Over the decade 2000-2009 and 2010-2019, there has been a significant rise in average maximum temperatures (table 3).

Table 3. Maximum temperature over the period 2000-2019 in Burkina Faso

n°	Name of region	Mean	Stdev	Min	Max	CV
1	Boucle du Mouhoun	35.21	0.82	32	37	2.33
2	Cascades	34.52	0.56	33	35	1.62
3	Central	35.06	0.23	35	36	0.66
4	Centre-East	36.71	0.61	35	38	1.66
5	North Central	35.33	0.47	34	36	1.33
6	Central-West	35.72	0.46	35	37	1.29
7	South Central	35.89	0.62	35	37	1.73
8	East	36.53	0.77	35	38	2.11
9	Hauts-Bassins	34.57	0.71	33	36	2.05
10	North	34.82	0.40	34	36	1.15
11	Plateau-Central	35.43	0.50	34	36	1.41
12	Sahel	35.41	0.49	34	36	1.38
13	SouthWest	35.62	0.56	34	37	1.57
2010-2019						
N°	Name of region	Mean	Stdev	Min	Max	CV
1	Boucle du Mouhoun	34.99	0.89	32	36	0.03
2	Cascades	34.38	0.57	33	35	0.02
3	Central	34.34	0.49	34	36	0.01
4	Centre-East	36.07	0.59	34	38	0.02
5	North Central	34.88	0.33	34	35	0.01
6	Central-West	35.42	0.53	34	36	0.01
7	South Central	35.64	0.56	34	37	0.02
8	East	35.66	0.83	35	38	0.02
9	Hauts-Bassins	34.46	0.73	33	36	0.02
10	North	34.33	0.47	33	35	0.01
11	Plateau-Central	34.88	0.67	34	36	0.02
12	Sahel	34.89	0.31	34	35	0.01
13	SouthWest	35.52	0.54	34	37	0.02

Source: Worldclim, 2000-2019

Spatial and temporal dynamics of the maximum temperatures in Burkina Faso between 1960 and 2019

Decadal dynamics of maximum temperatures in Burkina Faso between 1960 and 2019

Figure 2 below shows that the maximum temperatures change over the decades. Indeed,

the eastern, central-eastern, central-southern and central-western regions concentrate the maximum temperature episodes in the decades 1960-1969, 1970-1979, 1980-1989. However, in the decades 1990-1999, 2000-2009, 2010-2019, the hot spots are more oriented towards the eastern, central-eastern and central-southern regions.

Figure 2. Decadal dynamics of maximum temperatures in Burkina Faso from 1960 to 2019

Source: Worldclim, 1960-2019 ; 1= Boucle du Mouhoun, 2= Cascades ; 3= Central ; 4 = Central-East ; 5= North Central ; 6= Central-West ; 7= South Central; 8= East ; 9= Hauts-Bassins ; 10= North ; 11= Plateau-Central ; 12= Sahel ; 13= SouthWest

Seasonal dynamics of maximum temperatures in Burkina Faso from 1960 to 2019

Figure 3 below shows that the maximum temperatures developed in two phases. In the dry season, an increase in maximum temperatures can be seen between 1960 and 1989. Temperatures fluctuated between 37°C and 39°C. The regions affected also increased over the years. From 5 regions (East, Sahel, Central-West, Central Plateau, Central-East) in the decade 1960-1969, they increased to 7 regions (East, Boucle du Mouhoun, Central-West, Central Plateau, Central-East, South-West, Cascades) in the decade 1970-1979, then

to six (06) (East, Boucle du Mouhoun, Central-West, Central Plateau, Central-East, South-West). In the decades from 1990 to 2019, a decrease in maximum temperatures was observed, particularly in the number of regions affected, which varied between 2 and 3 (including the East, Centre-East, Centre-West).

Maximum temperatures during the rainy season are very high, ranging from 38°C to 40°C. Most of Burkina Faso's very hot zones are concentrated in the Sahel region. Conversely, the south-western regions of Burkina Faso experience lower temperatures during the rainy season.

Dry season 1970-1979

Rainy season 1970-1979

Dry season 1980-1989

Rainy season 1980-1989

Dry season 1990-1999

Rainy season 1990-1999

Dry season 2000-2009

Rainy season 2000-2009

Figure 3. Seasonal Evolution of Maximum Temperatures between 1960 and 2019 in Burkina Faso

Discussion

Annual Trends in Maximum Temperatures and Their Consequences in Africa

Annual maximum temperatures vary from region to region in Burkina Faso, but are also on the rise. These rising temperatures vary very little over the period in the country. Similarly, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2007) states that remarkable temperature changes (above the mean 0.5°C) were also reported between 1960 and 2009. These variations are confirmed by observations and projections by scientists around the world of climate alterations in the form of rising temperatures and changes in rainfall patterns (Chikosi et al., 2019). In West Africa, a significant increase in air temperature indicating projected and ongoing warming of up to 6.5°C was reported by M.A. Sylla et al. (2016, p.30). At country level, particularly in Burkina Faso, Bambara et al. (2018) note that cities such as Ouagadougou (Centre region) and Ouahigouya (North region) are experiencing rising temperatures. Thus, in Ouagadougou, between 1956-1985 and 1986-2015, average maximum temperature values rose from 38.2°C to 38.8°C over the period 1956-2015. The same observation was made in Ouahigouya. Between 1956-1985 and 1986-2015, the average

maximum temperature rose by 1°C (maximum temperature 39.6°C between 1956-1985 and 39.7°C between 1986-2015). In the province of Sissili, temperatures recorded at the Pô station from 1986 to 2018 show that the annual mean of the series is 28.4°C with a variation of $+1.2^{\circ}\text{C}$, reflecting an increase in temperature in the area (Sanou & Dipama, 2022).

In the Boulgou province (Centre-East region), Kima et al. (2015) also report that mean annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1980 to 2012 rose from 22.1°C to 34.4°C . In the Sahel region, in the rural commune of Seytenga, Zoma et al. (2022) find similar results for the increase in average temperatures from 1990 to 2019. SP/CONEDD (2007, p.4) also find that temperatures in Burkina Faso are rising sharply. Stalled (2012) states that temperatures have risen by 0.6°C in most of Burkina Faso since 1975. The rise in maximum temperatures has direct consequences for the people of Burkina Faso. A study carried out by Arisco et al, 2023 in Nouna (Boucle du Mouhoun) found that maximum temperatures of over 40°C increased the risk of death in children aged 0-5 years. In Botswana, higher maximum temperatures have an impact on the increased prevalence of diarrhoea in children (Alexander et al., 2013).

Conclusion

Maximum temperatures are particularly high in the Sahel, the Centre, the Centre-West, the Centre-South, the Boucle du Mouhoun and the South-West. There has been an upward trend in maximum temperatures from 1970 to 2019, with maximum temperatures in 2019 (34°C or 35°C on average) similar to those in the 1960-1969 decade (34°C or 35°C on average), which was a rainier period. We are also seeing a resurgence of the rainy phase over the period 2000-2019. There could be a link between the increase in maximum temperatures and the appearance of wet periods in Burkina Faso. It would be interesting to examine the link between maximum temperature and rainfall in Burkina Faso.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

Ahokpessi, Y. (2018). Analysis of the rainfall variability and change in the Republic of Benin (West Africa). *Hydrological sciences journal*, 63(15-16), 2097-2123. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667.2018.1554286>

Alexander, K. A., Carzolio, M., Goodin, D., & Vance, E. (2013). Climate change is likely to worsen the public health threat of diarrheal disease in Botswana. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 10(4), 1202–1230. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph10041202>

Arisco, N. J., Sewe, M. O., Bärnighausen, T., Sié, A., Zabre, P., & Bunker, A. (2023). The effect of extreme temperature and precipitation on cause-

specific deaths in rural Burkina Faso: a longitudinal study. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 7(6), 478-489. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(23\)00027-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(23)00027-X)

Bambara, D., Compaoré, H., & Bilgo, A. (2018). Évolution des températures au Burkina Faso entre 1956 et 2015: cas de Ouagadougou et de Ouahigouya. *Physio-Géo. Géographie physique et environnement*, 12, 23-41. <https://doi.org/10.4000/physio-geo.5688>

Barry, A.A., Caesar, J., Klein Tank, A.M.G., Aguilar, E., McSweeney, C., Cyrille, A.M., ... & Touray, L.M. (2018). West Africa climate extremes and climate change indices. *International Journal of Climatology*, 38, e921-e938. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5420>

Chikosi, E. S., Mugambiwa, S. S., Tirivangasi, H. M. & Rankoana, S. A. (2019). Climate change and variability perceptions in Ga-Dikgale community in Limpopo Province, South Africa. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, 11(3), 392-405. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-01-2018-0004>

Diouf, I., Fonseca, B.R., Caminade, C., Thiaw, W.M., Deme, A., Morse, A.P., ... & Ndiaye, M.K.N. (2020). Climate variability and malaria over West Africa. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 102(5), 1037-1047. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.19-0062>

GIEC. (2007). Résumé à l'intention des décideurs. In *Bilan 2007 des changements climatiques: Impacts, adaptation et vulnérabilité. Contribution du Groupe de travail II au quatrième Rapport d'évaluation*. Rapport du Groupe d'experts intergouvernemental sur l'évolution du climat, M.L. Parry, O.F. Canziani, J.P. Palutikof, P.J. van der Linden and C.E. Hanson, (éd.), Cambridge University Press, Belgique, Royaume-Uni.

Kima, S. A., Okhimamhe, A. A., Kiema, A., Zampaligre, N & Sule, I. (2015). Adapting to the impacts of climate change in the sub-humid zone of Burkina Faso, West Africa: Perceptions of agro-pastoralists. *Pastoralism: Research, Policy and Practice*, 5, 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13570-015-0034-9>

- Le Barbé, L., Lebel, T., & Tapsoba, D. (2002). Rainfall variability in West Africa during the years 1950–90. *Journal of climate*, 15(2), 187-202. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(2002\)015%3C0187:RVIWAD%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2002)015%3C0187:RVIWAD%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Nicholson, S. E. (2013). The West African Sahel: A review of recent studies on the rainfall regime and its interannual variability. *International Scholarly Research Notices*, 2013, 453521. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/453521>
- IPCC. (2021). *Summary for Policymakers. In: Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* In Press, 40.
- IPCC. (2022). Annex II: Glossary [Möller, V., R. van Diemen, J.B.R. Matthews, C. Méndez, S. Semenov, J.S. Fuglestedt, A. Reisinger (eds.)]. In *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, 2897-2930. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844.029>
- Hayelom, B., Chen, Y., Marsie, Z., & Negash, M. (2017). Temperature and precipitation trend analysis over the last 30 years in Southern Tigray Regional State, Ethiopia. *Journal of Atmospheric Pollution*, 5(1), 18-23. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201702.0014.v1>
- Medvigy, D., & Beaulieu, C. (2012). Trends in daily solar radiation and precipitation coefficients of variation since 1984. *Journal of Climate*, 25(4), 1330-1339. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1175/2011JCLI4115.1>
- NourEldeen, N., Mao, K., Yuan, Z., Shen, X., Xu, T., & Qin, Z. (2020). Analysis of the spatiotemporal change in land surface temperature for a long-term sequence in Africa (2003–2017). *Remote Sensing*, 12(3), 488. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12030488>.
- Nouaceur, Z., & Murarescu, O. (2020). Rainfall variability and trend analysis of rainfall in West Africa (Senegal, Mauritania, Burkina Faso). *Water*, 12(6), 1754. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12061754>
- Quenum, G. M. L. D., Nkrumah, F., Klutse, N. A. B., & Sylla, M. B. (2021). Spatiotemporal changes in temperature and precipitation in west Africa. Part I: Analysis with the CMIP6 historical dataset. *Water*, 13(24), 3506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13243506>
- Sanou, K & Dipama, J-M. (2022). Constraints and Prospects of rice Production in a Climate Change Context in the Sissili Province, Burkina Faso. *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 18 (23), 140-155.
- Stalled, R.R.H. (2012). *A Climate Trend Analysis of Burkina Faso. Famine Early Warning Systems Network-Informing Climate Change Adaptation Series.* USGS,4.
- SP/CONEDD. (2007). *Programme d'Action National d'Adaptation à la variabilité et aux changements climatiques (PANA) du Burkina Faso. Rapport du Ministère de l'environnement et du cadre de vie (MECV) et le Secrétariat Permanent du Conseil National pour l'Environnement et le Développement Durable, Ouagadougou.*
- Sylla, M. B., Nikiema, P. M., Gibba, P., Kebe, I., Klutse, N. A. B. (2016). Climate Change over West Africa: Recent Trends and Future Projections: in Yaro J., Hesselberg J. (eds) *Adaptation to Climate Change and Variability in Rural West Africa.* Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31499-0_3.
- Zoma, V., Tarama, W. J.I., & Ouédraogo, J. (2022). Variabilité climatique dans la commune rurale de Seytenga au Burkina Faso. *Les cahiers de l'acaref*, 4(8), 320-334.